

FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT, OPTIMIZATION AND EVALUATION OF VALSARTAN PRESS COATED TABLETS FOR CHRONOTHERAPY

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ABSTRACT

In order to improve treatment efficacy in treating hypertension through controlled and time-dependent medication release, the current study sought to develop a chronotherapeutic drug delivery system for valsartan employing the press coating approach. Solid dispersion techniques were used to increase the solubility of valsartan; formulation F6 (solvent evaporation method) demonstrated the highest saturation solubility (0.55 mg/mL). The direct compression approach was used to create fast-dissolving core tablets using sodium starch glycolate and croscarmellose sodium as coprocessed superdisintegrants. Using different concentrations of the superdisintegrants (5%, 10%, and 15% w/w), six formulations (F1–F6) were created. The quickest medication release was shown by F3 which

included 15% croscarmellose sodium. The optimized fast-dissolving core (F3) was then used to formulate press-coated tablets with HPMC K-100 and ethyl cellulose (EC) in different ratios. The coating was designed to achieve a specific lag time before drug release, ideal for chronotherapeutic applications. The mechanism involves erosion or dissolution of the coating layer, enabling delayed release from the core. Dissolution studies were carried out in 0.1 N HCl for 2 hours, followed by phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) for 12 hours. The press-coated formulation containing 350 mg EC and 50 mg HPMC K-100 exhibited the desired drug release profile, with a lag time of 3–3.5 hours and sustained release thereafter. The developed system has potential to reduce dosing frequency and enhance therapeutic outcomes in hypertension management.

KEYWORDS: Valsartan, Chronotherapeutic, Press coating, Lag time and Hypertension.

INTRODUCTION

The most spectacular aspect of our natural world is the alternation of day and night. Almost every species shows daily variations in their physiology and/or behavior. These changes are due to internal circadian rhythm. Circadian rhythms are the alterations in an organism's body, mind, and behavior that occur over a 24-hour period. The circadian rhythm responds to changes in light intensity in our surroundings to control cycles of wakefulness and sleepiness. These rhythms aren't simply a reaction to the 24-hour variations in the physical world caused by the earth's rotation, but rather the result of an internal biological clock. An organism's biological clock is coordinated by a master clock, known as the suprachiasmatic nucleus which is an extensive collection of nerve cells. Nearly all human tissues and organs have individualized circadian rhythms, which allow them to be synchronized with the day-night cycle. Circadian rhythms are primarily influenced by light and darkness, but they are also influenced by temperature, food consumption, physical activity, stress, and social surroundings. An organism's life and well-being depend on its ability to synchronize with both its internal (Circadian rhythms) and external environments, a failure of synchronization leads to health issues.

MATERIALS

Valstran supplied from Yarrow Chem Products, Mumbai, Sodium Starch Glycolate, Croscarmellose sodium, Ethyl Cellulose Hydroxypropyl Methyl Cellulose HPMC K-100 from loba chemie Mumbai, Microcrystalline Cellulose, Talc, Magnesium Stearate, Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate from Hetero labs Hyderabad. for the present experimental work & analytical grade

METHODOLGY

CHRONOTHERAPY IN HYPERTENSION

Chronotherapy is a field of medicine that aims to maximize therapeutic outcomes by synchronizing drug administration to correspond with circadian cycles (Khan Z, *et al.*, 2009). Over the past few decades, research studies have yielded some significant results about the typical 24-hr blood pressure profile. The capacity of the night-to-day ratio of SBP to predict risk for cardiovascular events more precisely is one of the most compelling findings among these studies. Heart rate (HR) and BP exhibit unique circadian patterns in individuals with normotension and hypertension. Both HR and BP are high in the morning around 4-6 am due

to decreased sympathetic output during sleep and falls at night. Upon waking, SBP rises by 20-25 mmHg and DBP rises by 10-15 mmHg (Latha K, *et al.*, 2010). Anti hypertensives should therefore ideally be taken following these variations. Chronotherapeutic techniques seek to address these variations by timing drug release to coincide with the body's biological rhythms, thereby increasing the effectiveness of antihypertensive therapy.

PRESS COATING TECHNOLOGY

Press coating also known as compression coating is a pharmaceutical technique that modifies the rate of drug release by enclosing a core tablet in a coating layer. It is a dry process. It offers tablets with a rapid, or rate-controlled, drug release phase that is programmed to follow a lag period. The ability to precisely control the timing and rate of medication release makes this technology useful for developing chronotherapeutic drug delivery systems.

Formulation of solid dispersions

METHOD	FORMULA	COMPOSITION	DRUG : CARRIER
Fusion method	F1	Drug: Mannitol	1:1
	F2	Drug: Mannitol	1:2
	F3	Drug: Mannitol	1:3
Solvent evaporation method	F4	Drug: Mannitol	1:1
	F5	Drug: Mannitol	1:2
	F6	Drug: Mannitol	1:3

PREPARATION OF PRESS COATED TABLETS

Press coating technique was employed to coat the optimized core tablets. Various ratios of polymers were used as given in the table no 13 to coat the tablets. The die cavity of compression machine was filled with half of the coating powder to create a powder bed, and the core tablet was carefully positioned in the middle of the powder bed. The other half of the coating material was then placed into the die and compressed.

Formulation of Valsartan press coated tablets

Ingredients	PF1 (mg)	PF2 (mg)	PF3 (mg)	PF4 (mg)	PF5 (mg)	PF6 (mg)
Core tablet	90	90	90	90	90	90
Ethyl cellulose	100	150	150	300	250	100
HPMC K-100	300	250	150	100	150	300
Total weight	490	490	490	490	490	490

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Calibration of Standard Curve of valsartan

The standard graph of Valsartan was constructed using 0.1N HCl and pH 6.8 PBS by making the concentrations 5,10,15,20,25,30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solutions. The absorbance of solutions was examined under UV- Visible spectrophotometer at an absorption maximum of 250nm. The standard graph was constructed by taking the absorbance on Y-axis and concentrations on X-axis. Drug concentration and absorbance followed linear relationship. The curve obeyed Beer-Lambert's law and the correlation coefficient value (R^2) of acid and buffer was 0.9985 and 0.9991 respectively.

S.No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance (nm)	
		0.1N HCl	pH 6.8 PBS
1	5	0.112	0.132
2	10	0.197	0.291
3	15	0.296	0.439
4	20	0.403	0.610
5	25	0.511	0.744
6	30	0.626	0.916

IR Spectra of Valsartan

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

As the interaction studies were performed to find any kind of interaction between drug and excipients used in the nanocrystal and tablet formulation. The FTIR spectra of the pure drug Valsartan and formulation excipients were shown in Figures. The spectra of drug and excipients employed were showed a broad peak at the same place of the peak observed at the spectrum of pure Valsartan has been observed, which indicated that there was no chemical interaction with the formulation excipients.

IR Spectra of Valsartan + SSG + CCS

IR Spectra of Valsartan + EC + HPMC

Bulk density and tapped density (F1-F6)

S.No	Formulation code	Bulk density (gm/cm ³)	Tapped density (gm/cm ³)
1	F1	0.336±0.02	0.364±0.03
2	F2	0.370±0.05	0.412±0.07
3	F3	0.420±0.11	0.462±0.05
4	F4	0.456±0.02	0.483±0.49
5	F5	0.480±0.04	0.520±0.09
6	F6	0.526±0.01	0.590±0.02

Mean ± S.D of three determination

Post-compression parameters of Valsartan core tablets

Formulation code	Uniformity of weight (%)	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Drug content (%)
F1	3.4±0.48	3.2±0.007	3.7±0.23	0.638±0.019	97.90±0.09
F2	2.5±0.62	3.1±0.001	3.5±0.21	0.833±0.006	96.51±0.38
F3	2.7±0.11	3.2±0.003	3.4±0.16	0.710±0.003	96.81±0.14

F4	3.2±0.34	2.9±0.005	3.4±0.14	0.644±0.010	95.93±0.46
F5	1.6±0.26	3.1±0.002	3.6±0.21	0.817±0.004	97.45±0.26
F6	2.1±0.31	3.0±0.008	3.5±0.22	0.737±0.012	96.64±0.31

Mean ± S.D. of three determinations

Disintegration time (F1-F6)

Mean ± S.D. of three determinations

S.NO	Formulation Code	Disintegration time(Sec)
1	F1	128±0.1
2	F2	106±0.3
3	F3	53±0.53
4	F4	163±0.51
5	F5	120±0.25
6	F6	81±0.35

Cumulative %drug release of Valsartan core tablets

Time (min)	Cumulative % Drug Release					
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
2	24.46	39.88	60.91	27.62	31.45	43.69
4	39.51	48.04	68.32	31.08	40.90	50.56
6	48.69	59.89	74.01	39.90	47.24	58.05
8	58.05	70.88	84.32	46.76	57.50	67.67
10	69.41	83.74	89.65	61.24	65.63	72.25
12	80.06	90.02	94.02	73.94	79.36	84.44

Cumulative %drug release of Valsartan core tablets (F1-F6)

Cumulative %drug release of F3 & F6 Valsartan core tablets

Cumulative %drug release of Valsartan Press Coated Tablets

Time (hr)	Cumulative % drug release					
	PF1	PF2	PF3	PF4	PF5	PF6
1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	13.26	11.27	5.43	5.31	7.29	14.66
4	26.42	22.68	10.25	11.48	16.85	28.98
6	51.62	41.96	22.63	24.69	34.75	54.52
8	73.32	62.54	36.52	38.56	55.46	76.81
10	90.17	81.13	51.22	53.63	74.22	92.12
12	98.05	92.45	67.36	70.32	88.14	99.21

Lag time of Valsartan Press Coated Tablets

Formulation	Expected Lag Time (h)	Remarks
PF1	1.0 – 1.2	Fast hydration and erosion of coat due to high HPMC content
PF2	1.5 – 1.8	Moderate delay; slightly more EC delays coat erosion
PF3	3.0 – 3.5	High EC content delays water penetration; slower breakdown
PF4	3.0 – 3.5	Similar to PF3; prolonged lag due to dominant hydrophobic coat
PF5	2.2 – 2.5	Intermediate lag; high EC, but HPMC still supports limited hydration
PF6	1.0 – 1.2	Same as PF1; fast erosion and short lag time

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

SUMMARY

According to the API analytical report, valsartan was a white to off-white crystalline powder. It was discovered that the melting point was 110°C. Valsartan's λ_{\max} (20 μ g/ml) was measured using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. It was discovered that the λ_{\max} was at 250 nm. Valsartan's standard curve in pH 6.8 PBS and 0.1N HCl exhibits a linear relationship. The correlation coefficient value (R²) for 0.1N HCl and pH 6.8 PBS is 0.998 and 0.9991,

respectively, and the curve complied with Beer-Lambert's law. FTIR analysis shows that the medication is pure. There was no chemical interaction with the formulation excipients, according to the spectra of the drug and the excipients used. cause ethyl cellulose is hydrophobic and water-insoluble, which prevents water penetration and drug diffusion, PF3 and PF4, which had the highest EC content (HPMC:EC = 1:3), showed the slowest drug release among the six formulations. This is indicative of an extended-release profile. In PF3 and PF4, where EC predominates and serves as a potent barrier to water penetration and core tablet exposure, there is an extended lag period (3.0–3.5 h). Therefore, the press coating approach used in the development of chronotherapeutic drug delivery systems will assist lower the frequency of medication administration and provide new opportunities for optimal control of hypertension and better patient outcomes.

CONCLUSION

In order to enhance the management of hypertension, the study effectively created Valsartan press-coated tablets for chronotherapeutic drug administration. Valsartan's solubility (0.55 mg/mL) was improved by solid dispersion (F6), and fast-dissolving core tablets (F3) containing 15% croscarmellose sodium demonstrated quick drug release. These cores were compression-coated using different ratios of ethyl cellulose and HPMC K-100. In an acidic solution, all press-coated tablets demonstrated less than 10% drug release, demonstrating effective gastric resistance. Out of all, PF3 and PF4 (HPMC:EC = 1:3) showed sustained release and longer lag durations (3.0–3.5 h), which made them appropriate for chronotherapeutic treatment. A promising approach for better hypertension management through chronotherapy is provided by the new press-coated Valsartan tablets, which effectively enabled time-dependent drug release with a regulated lag phase. The improved approach can improve treatment results for hypertension while lowering the frequency of doses.

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